

THE FRACTURE OF NANOSILICA AND RUBBER TOUGHENED EPOXY FIBRE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Epoxy matrix fibre composites have been modified with the addition of rubber and nanosilica particles. Fracture studies conducted on the bulk matrix and composite show a synergistic effect between the nanosilica and rubber, resulting in a 50% increase in bulk fracture energy in an anhydride cured system.

Keywords: fracture, nanocomposite, nanosilica, rubber toughening, fibre composite, interfacial adhesion

INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins are favourable as matrices in fibre reinforced composites due to their high crosslink densities. This results in good thermal stability and creep resistance. However, this also results in the composite being brittle and having a poor resistance to fracture and delamination.

The addition of rubber particles increases the fracture toughness while decreasing the stiffness of the material, [1]. This has been successfully overcome by adding rigid particles such as nanosilica to the epoxy [2]. A synergistic effect has been observed in nanosilica and rubber toughened epoxies, with significant increases in toughness without any observable change in the glass transition temperature, T_g or change in stiffness. The use of a soluble rubber addition and 20nm silica particles is well suited to low - cost composite manufacturing processes such as resin infusion under flexible tooling or vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding. Due to the scales associated with the particles; they are not filtered out by the fibre reinforcements during infusion. Previous work [3, 4] has shown that fibre composites can be successfully manufactured and give an increase in toughness. It has also been shown that improved fatigue thresholds can be achieved with the addition of nanosilica [5].

In the present work, results from mode I fracture of bulk and composite systems are reported for two systems. The first is an anhydride - cured DGEBA formulation that has a low viscosity and low temperature cure. These properties make it suitable for applications involving infusion of large structures such as wind turbine blades or marine structures using glass fibre reinforcement. The second is an amine - cured

tetrafunctional - epoxide. This is more highly crosslinked meaning the matrix is stiffer and more thermally stable; suiting it to high performance applications with carbon fibre reinforcement. Interestingly, both matrices have similar bulk fracture energies of 70-80J/m². Toughening mechanisms have been investigated for the bulk matrix using plane strain compression and double - notched four - point bend tests on the bulk polymer. Evidence of toughening will be presented experimentally with an explanation of the mechanisms that have been observed.

MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURE

Two systems have been compared in this work. Firstly a DGEBA, 'LY556' (Huntsman) cured with an accelerated methylhexahydrophthalic acid anhydride: 'Albidur HE 600' (Nanoresins) at stoichiometry for use in a glass fibre composite system (anhydride system). Secondly, a TGMDA, 'Epikote 496' (Nanoresins) cured with a 'Lonzacure' (Lonza group) M-DEA(79%)/M-DIPA(21%) amine at stoichiometry for use in a carbon fibre composite system (amine system). Both of these systems can be likened to commercially available resins for their respective applications.

Organosilane - modified nanosilica was obtained at 40wt% in its respective base resin; 'Nanopox F400' and 'Bakelite EPR 486' (Nanoresins). The nanoparticles have an average particle size of about 20nm [6] and have been shown to be well dispersed in the base resins.

The rubber used is a carboxylterminated butadiene - acrylonitrile (CTBN) rubber, 'Hypro CTBN 1300x8' (Emerald Performance Materials) which has been pre-reacted with the resin to give a 40wt% CTBN - epoxy adduct; 'Albipox 1000' and 'Albipox XP 23/0206' (Nanoresins).

Formulations have been manufactured based on the percentage weight by total mass of matrix with modifier. Therefore the systems that have been explored are a control, 10%wt nanosilica, 20%wt nanosilica, 9%wt CTBN and a 10%wt nanosilica/9% CTBN hybrid. The formulations were prepared by mixing the components to give the required amounts of nanosilica and rubber. This was conducted at an elevated temperature prior to addition of hardener to ensure good dispersion. Bulk specimens were cast in steel gravity moulds and degassed prior to curing to ensure void - free bulk specimens. The anhydride system was mixed at 60°C, and cured using a cure cycle of 1 hour at 90°C followed by a 2 hour post cure at 160°C. The amine system was mixed at a temperature of 120°C, followed by a cure cycle of 2 hours at 180°C.

Composite plates were manufactured by resin infusion under flexible tooling (RIFT). Two fabrics have been used to produce the different composite plates. Quasi-isotropic plates were manufactured using a biaxial stitched non-crimp fabric 'XE450/1200' and 'XC411/1270 (HSC)' (SP Systems). Composite plates approximately 4mm thick were prepared using 8 plies, arranged in a balanced symmetric lay-up to give a 0°/0° interface for fracture testing. A 12.5µm thick Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) film was inserted into the fabric prior to resin infusion to act as a starter crack for the fracture specimens. The degassed resin was drawn through the fibres at their respective mixing temperatures, using a vacuum to achieve a void-free composite. The plates were cured as per their aforementioned cured cycles. The composite panels were imaged using a

water immersed C-scan to ensure that they had been well infused. This was more relevant to the amine/carbon system since the anhydride/glass FRP is translucent.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The glass transition temperature, T_g was measured using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). 10mg samples of each formulation were heated through two cycles of the range 20°C to 200°C at 10°C/min. T_g was defined as the point of inflexion for an energy input versus temperature curve.

Single edge notch bend (SENB) tests were conducted on bulk polymer samples to obtain values for the initiation fracture energy, G_C and fracture toughness, K_{IC} . Tests were conducted in accordance to ISO 13586 [7] and ASTM D5045-91a [8]. A rectangular sample was cut to the required dimension and notched. A natural crack was introduced by tapping with a liquid nitrogen cooled razor blade into the notch.

The composite mode I fracture energy, G_{IC} was measured using the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test. The fracture energy was calculated using the 'corrected beam theory' method [9].

Plane strain compression tests have been conducted on the bulk polymers in accordance to work by Williams and Ford [10]. Due to thermoset polymer's inherent brittleness, it is impossible to achieve high strains in tension without resulting in premature fracture. This test method gives the ability to probe the toughening mechanisms by generating extensive shear yielding.

Double - notch four - point bend tests were conducted to generate sub - critically loaded crack tips [11]. A bulk specimen is produced with two pre - cracks in the gauge area. When loaded in four - point bending, the two cracks will experience the same stress state with one of the cracks reaching a critical K_{IC} . The second crack will have experienced almost the same stress intensity K and hence, will have an almost critical process zone at the crack tip.

RESULTS

DSC results show that the glass transition temperature changes very little for the formulations. The addition of nanosilica and CTBN rubber has very little effect to the overall glass transition temperatures. Separate tests on the composite and bulk systems show good agreement. This suggests that there is no change in the crosslink density of the epoxy for the different modifications. A T_g of 140°C was measured for the anhydride formulation. The amine system has been found to show a T_g of 180°C.

Optical microscopy has been conducted on polished cross sections of the composites. These have been used to confirm that the composites are well consolidated and free of voids. The composites have a typical fibre volume fraction of about 57%.

Morphology

Figure 1 shows the bulk morphology using phase images from atomic force microscopy (AFM) from [12]. It can be seen in the control specimens (Figure 1a and 1e) that the

surfaces are featureless and homogenous apart from some cutting lines as result of microtoming.

The CTBN rubber undergoes reaction - induced phase separation upon curing. AFM has shown that the typical particle size of rubber is about $1\mu\text{m}$ for the anhydride system (Figure 1b). The nanosilica remains well dispersed in the anhydride system (Figure 1c) but seems to agglomerate into small clusters ($\sim 5 - 6$ particles) in the amine system (Figure 1g).

Figure 1 – Phase images from AFM to show bulk morphology for the anhydride (a-d) and amine (e-h) formulations.

When the hybrid formulation is cured and the CTBN phase separates, the nanosilica in the mix is mobilised in both systems. Subsequently, small agglomerations of nanosilica which themselves are well dispersed form in the matrix. The CTBN rubber particle size increases to $1.5\mu\text{m}$ in the anhydride [4] but is unchanged in the amine system.

A similar morphology has been observed in the fibre inter-space of the composite using AFM and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). This has been obtained by micro-potting a composite sample from the RIFT process and preparing the surface with the microtome; just as the bulk. This suggests that the fibres do not filter out the nanosilica, Figure 2.

Figure 2 – AFM of anhydride 10%wt nanosilica glass fibre composite.

Fracture Tests

Mode I fracture tests have been conducted for the bulk and composite to obtain the initiation fracture energy, shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Fracture tests for the bulk and composite systems.

The bulk initiation was calculated at the point of fracture; which was observed to be in a brittle manner for all formulations. For mode I tests on the composite, initiation was calculated by examining the visual, non-linear and 5% offset/max criteria and taking the lower bound value [9].

Results for the anhydride system show that there is little effect on the toughness with the addition of nanosilica, with a modest increase in the bulk fracture energy and no change in the composite. There is a synergy in the hybrid bulk with a total increase of 650% compared to the unmodified epoxy and 50% larger than the rubber-modified epoxy. The composite shows a clear increase with the addition of rubber to 1kJ/m^2 . The improved composite properties in the hybrid cannot be confirmed due to the large experimental error in the results. The amine system shows a 50% improvement in bulk fracture energy with the addition of nanosilica. However, composite properties are decreased with the addition of nanosilica. Whilst there is a large improvement in matrix toughness with the addition of rubber, the properties do not transfer to the composite.

The observed increase in the toughness of the rubber - modified epoxies can be explained as enhanced deformation of the epoxy due to interactions between rubber particles and the epoxy ahead of the crack tip [13]. The further increase of toughness in the hybrid has been postulated as plastic void formation around the nanosilica particles during fracture. This has not been seen in the amine system because the system is more highly cross-linked, thus less able to deform plastically. The increase in toughness with the addition of nanosilica to the epoxies is low.

Plane Strain Compression

Results from plane strain compression tests for the bulk anhydride cured epoxy are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Engineering stress versus strain for the anhydride - cured epoxy with varying nanosilica content.

It can be seen in Figure 4 that after the initial linear elastic loading, the epoxy reaches the compressive yield strength. Generally; tensile specimens will fracture before the yield point; showing the importance of the strains that can be achieved with this test. The epoxy then strain softens. Strain softening can facilitate extensive shear yielding in the matrix and allows voiding to occur around particles, as shown by Kawaguchi and Pearson, [14]. With increasing strain, the stress can be seen to increase again as the polymer work hardens. Interestingly, it can be seen that the yield strength does not vary with change in nanocontent. Much of the work with rubber - toughened epoxies has shown that decreasing the yield strength to allow matrices to shear yield; resulting in increased toughness.

Figure 5 - Engineering stress versus strain for the amine - cured epoxy with varying nanosilica content.

Plane strain tests with the amine system show very different interfacial properties, see Figure 5. It can be seen that the yield strength increases with nanosilica content. Furthermore, the matrix does not strain soften significantly. Therefore the matrix does not facilitate shear yielding and subsequent void growth around particles as shown in [6]. As with the anhydride system, an increase in compressive modulus can be seen along with a greater extent of work hardening with increase in nanocontent.

Toughening Mechanisms

Double notch four point bend tests have been conducted with the nanosilica modified formulations. Figure 6 shows the vicinity of the crack tip using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) of an 80nm slice taken from a cross section at the centre of the specimen. This allows examination of the process zone region that is created under plane strain conditions. It is evident that there is extensive shear yielding in the matrix. The specimen varies in thickness, and a clear region in the image can be seen which is

lighter in colour. This is an artefact of specimen preparation since any residual stresses in the mid plane are relaxed as the specimen is sectioned and the specimen mid plane becomes a free surface.

It is evident that the nanosilica particles have debonded at the poles; some of these are circled in Figure 6. It is noteworthy that even in an elastically unloaded specimen; this debonded region can be seen clearly. This is an indication that plastic deformation has occurred.

Figure 6 – Crack tip of sub - critically loaded sample of anhydride cured 10%wt nanosilica.

Work by Chen et al. [15] has examined the effect of particle size on energy dissipation in nanocomposites. It can be shown analytically using [16], that the energy dissipation due to interfacial debonding is very small as particle size approaches a tens of nanometres in scale, of the order of $0.1\text{J}/\text{m}^2$ as correctly postulated by Johnsen *et al.*[6]. Hence, it is the void growth mechanism that gives the toughening effect. This suggests that a weaker interface is favourable for obtaining better toughening by decreasing the stress required to debond the particle. Their void growth model tended to over - predict the toughness due to the assumption that all particles were considered to contribute to plastic void growth. This has been refined by using SEM images of fracture surfaces of the nanosilica only samples. By discretising the void growth that has been observed, it has been possible to quantify that approximately 60% of the particles on the fracture surface have debonded at the equator. Of these, 15% of the particles observed have been found to show extensive void growth. Since we have already concluded that the contribution of debonding is negligible, if we consider the void growth contribution for 15% of the particles in a 14.8%wt (10% vol.) nanosilica, then $G_c = 132\text{J}/\text{m}^2$. This has been measured experimentally to be about $190\text{J}/\text{m}^2$. This shows good agreement when

considering that the calculated toughness will be an underestimate as it has no contribution of a shear banding term; originally postulated by Huang and Kinloch, [16].

CONCLUSIONS

Modified fibre composites with increased toughness have been produced without detriment to flexural modulus or the glass transition temperature. Matrix morphologies in the bulk and composite are similar, indicating that RIFT does not filter out the particles during infusion. The anhydride system shows good dispersion in the nanosilica only samples, but the nanosilica tends to agglomerate when the CTBN phase - separates in the hybrid formulations. In the amine system, the nanosilica does not stay well dispersed, resulting in small nanosilica clusters. Results for the anhydride system demonstrate that there is a transfer of toughness to the composite from the increases that have been observed in the bulk. The amine shows little toughenability when nanosilica is added in the composite. This could be due to the agglomerated nature of the particles. Furthermore the amine does not show any synergistic toughening effect unlike the anhydride system.

Examination of the yield strength from plane strain compression tests on the bulk demonstrates that the interfacial properties of the two systems appear to be very different. The anhydride system has very low interfacial adhesion with the matrix whilst the amine is well bonded.

Examination of analytical models show that the energy associated with debonding particles is insignificant. The modified model agrees well to experimental values, suggesting that the increased toughness is obtained by allowing the matrix to plastically deform. However, a shear banding term is necessary to examine the contribution of void growth compared to formation of shear yielding. Since plastic deformation of the matrix is a key parameter, it appears that lower T_g and hence lower yield strength resins are easier to toughen.

So far, imaging of the nanoparticles in the hybrid systems has been obscured by the presence of rubber, resulting in very rough fracture surfaces. Work will continue to extend the theory to explain toughening mechanisms in the hybrid system using double - notch four - point bend tests.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors wish to thank the EPSRC for the studentship of K. Masania and acknowledge the general support from the US Army European Research Office and Emerald Performance Materials. The authors acknowledge T.H. Hsieh and J. Sohn Lee for their contributions to the experimental work.

References

1. Kinloch, A.J., *Theme Article - Toughening Epoxy Adhesives to Meet Today's Challenges*. Materials Research Society Bulletin, 2003. 28(6): p. 445-448.
2. Kinloch, A.J., R. Mohammed, A.C. Taylor, C. Eger, S. Sprenger, and D. Egan, *The effect of silica nano particles and rubber particles on the toughness of*

- multiphase thermosetting epoxy polymers*. Journal of Materials Science, 2005. 40(18): p. 5083-5086.
3. Kinloch, A.J., R.D. Mohammed, A.C. Taylor, S. Sprenger, and D. Egan, *The interlaminar toughness of carbon-fibre reinforced plastic composites using 'hybrid-toughened' matrices*. Journal of Materials Science, 2006. 41(15): p. 5043-5046.
 4. Kinloch, A.J., K. Masania, R.D. Mohammed, A.C. Taylor, and S. Sprenger, *Toughness of nanoparticle-modified epoxy and fibre composites*. Proceedings of the 31st Annual Meeting of the Adhesion Society, 2007.
 5. Blackman, B.R.K., A.J. Kinloch, J. Sohn Lee, A.C. Taylor, R. Agarwal, G. Schueneman, and S. Sprenger, *The fracture and fatigue behaviour of nano-modified epoxy polymers*. Journal of Materials Science, 2007. 42(16): p. 7049-7051.
 6. Johnsen, B.B., A.J. Kinloch, R.D. Mohammed, A.C. Taylor, and S. Sprenger, *Toughening mechanisms of nanoparticle-modified epoxy polymers*. Polymer, 2007. 48(2): p. 530-541.
 7. BS/ISO-13586, *Plastics - Determination of fracture toughness (K_c and G_c) - Linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) approach in BS*. 2000.
 8. D5045-91a, *Standard Test Methods for Plain-Strain Fracture Toughness and Strain Energy Release Rate of Plastic Materials*, in ASTM. 1991.
 9. D5528, *Standard Test Method for Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fibre Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites*. 1994, ASTM.
 10. Williams, J.G. and H. Ford, *Stress - Strain Relationships For Some Unreinforced Plastics* Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science, 1964. 6(4): p. 405-417.
 11. Yee, A.F. and H.J. Sue, *Study of fracture mechanisms of multiphase polymers using the double-notch four-point-bending method*. Journal of materials science, 1993. 28(11): p. 2975-2980.
 12. Mohammed, R.D., *Material Properties and Fracture mechanisms of Epoxy Nano composites*, PhD Thesis, Mechanical Engineering, Imperial College London, 2007
 13. Kinloch, A.J., S.J. Shaw, D.A. Tod, and D.L. Hunston, *Deformation and fracture behaviour of a rubber-toughened epoxy: 1. Microstructure and fracture studies*. Polymer, 1983. 24(10): p. 1341-1354.
 14. Kawaguchi, T., *The effect of particle-matrix adhesion on the mechanical behavior of glass filled epoxies: Part 1. A study on yield behavior and cohesive strength*. Polymer, 2003. 44(15): p. 4229.
 15. Chen, J.-K., Z.-P. Huang, and J. Zhu, *Size effect of particles on the damage dissipation in nanocomposites*. Composites Science and Technology, 2007. 67(14): p. 2990-2996.
 16. Huang, Y., *Modelling of the toughening mechanisms in rubber-modified epoxy polymers*. Journal of Materials Science, 1992. 27(10): p. 2763-2769.